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BUSINESS PLAN: OPENING OF THE BISTRÔ DO BIFF CASA DE CARNES BRANCH, AVENIDA SÃO JOÃO APARECIDA DE GOIÂNIA GO

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this project is to make available to the consumer market a new meat shop offering products with quality standards, certified by the Sanitary Surveillance and Procon. An entrepreneurial strategy defined for differentiation and positioning in the market are the Barbecue Meat Kits with attractive prices, whose different personalized cuts meet the customer's needs.